

pya – a Python Library for Audio Processing and Auditory Display

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces *pya*, a python package for audio processing and sound and music computing (SMC). We focus on the key concepts, the core classes for signals, spectra and spectrograms, furthermore we illustrate the supported interaction types and different use cases. The examples focus on (i) sound synthesis, (ii) multi-channel audio processing, and (iii) sonification, specifically audification and parameter-mapping sonification. We showcase how *pya* facilitates advanced audio processing. Finally we provide a roadmap for future development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Researchers and developers need tools and software environments to sketch ideas, to prototype, develop, test, and evaluate novel systems, and thereby to advance the state-of-the-art in their discipline. Particularly in the field of sound and music computing (SMC), including auditory display research, sound design, digital audio effects, machine listening, music information retrieval (MIR), to name a few, tools for just-in-time creation of – and interaction with – code, user controls, sound, and algorithms are crucial. At the same time, researchers wish to document their steps, visualize results, and format their system in a reproducible, shareable form.

The Open Source programming language Python has grown for decades into a very mature interactive programming ecosystem, which – supported by powerful packages such as the NumPy [1], SciPy [2], Matplotlib [3], scikit-learn [4]– offers wonderful and highly flexible means for data scientists. Furthermore Jupyter notebooks and Jupyter Lab enable Web-browser-based interactions in a just-in-time manner, enabling to interleave code and documentation. So, data scientists often prefer code-oriented platforms such as MATLAB, Octave, and Python. Particularly for Python, NumPy offers ndarray as a suitable representation for multi-channel audio data, and SciPy features powerful functions for digital signal processing, such as via

`scipy.signal`. Interestingly, research on digital audio signal processing often uses other platforms, such as C/C++, MATLAB. There are also specialized sound synthesis and audio processing languages/tools such as SuperCollider, PureData, Max, Csound, Chuck, Faust, which, however, are more focused on sound design and real-time rendering and less flexible on accessing the data vector for subsequent inspection or analysis. So why not simply use (and add convenient) functions for loading, saving, recording and playing audio and work as such? One reason is that audio signals are not just a data vector or multi-dimensional array: meta data, such as sampling rate, channel names, value range, may vary and need to be specified and provided every time for functions to work properly. This causes substantial coding overhead and makes writing code even for simple audio signal processing tasks less elegant – and in turn, it makes the code harder to read.

For instance, to create 1 second, 2-channel 44100 Hz audio signal and to play its segment from 0.5s and 0.7s in plain Python with NumPy and sounddevice takes

```
1 sr, nr_chnls, duration = 44100, 2, 1.0
2 signal = np.zeros((sr*duration, nr_chnls))
3 sounddevice.play(signal[int(0.5*sr), int(0.7*sr)], fs=sr)
```

whereas *pya*'s `Asig` and *time slice indexing* condenses the above to

```
1 a = Asig(1.0, sr=44100, channels=2)[{0.5:0.7}].play()
```

while enabling later attribute access via `a.channels`, `a.sr`, `a.get_duration()`. The advantages become even more obvious as code grows.

There are several existing audio packages within the Python ecosystem. To our knowledge, they mostly fall into two categories: 1) toolkits for audio signal analysis; 2) audio synthesis and I/O. Analytical toolkits such as `pyAudioAnalysis`, `LibROSA`, `SpeechRecognition` and `madmon` [5–8] all have a strong focus on music information retrieval (MIR) and machine learning. They provide useful functions for audio signal feature extraction, segmentation and classification. These packages gear more toward offline processing of audio arrays and less so on applications in audio I/O. On the second category, there are multiple packages for ‘low-level’ access to audio hardware and audio files (e.g. `PyAudio`, `playsound`, `simpleaudio`, `audiooop`, `sound`), they are more of a barebone package on top of which programmers still need to develop their own synthesis and processing from scratch. An exception is

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pyo, a powerful package designed for real-time sound synthesis and signal processing. Its design philosophy is reminiscent of SuperCollider [9] for sound design and composition. Yet to our limited knowledge, pyo's PyObject is not a static storage for samples but rather a buffer. Thus interactions between a NumPy array and pyo's processing functions are not straightforward. Pydub and Pygame offers easy-to-use audio manipulation but gear more towards application audio such as games, hence they lack more in-depth processing functionalities and support for sample-accurate indexing [10, 11].

In summary, while there are a number of audio packages available, each has certain trade-offs that ultimately led us to developing pya for all our needs, including a clean coding interface, NumPy-focused editing and processing, multi-channel support, sample-precise indexing, easy access to files and audio hardware and builtin methods for plotting. To not reinvent the wheel, pya embraces existing cross-platform low-level audio interfaces, specifically PyAudio, which in turn relies on the C/C++ audio API portaudio.

The paper starts with an introduction to the core pya classes Asig, Aspec and Astft, and to the interface class Aserver. It introduces key concepts to keep an as-clean-as-possible, pythonic interface and providing minimal code examples. In Section 4, we illustrate how pya can be used in selected use cases, namely sound synthesis, multi-channel audio processing, and offline-rendered audifications and parameter-mapping sonifications. We wrap up with a short discussion and conclusion.

2. LIBRARY OVERVIEW AND FEATURES

pya aims to fuse together the advantages of array processing with NumPy and PyAudio to enable users to easily create, analyze, manipulate, record and play multi-channel audio signals. It facilitates method chaining, which is particularly useful when applying multiple processing steps, such as below where multiple processes including signal manipulations, plotting and playback can be daisy-chained together.

```
1 asig.gain(db=6).fade_out(0.2).pan2(-0.5).iirfilter
   (200).plot('r-').play(rate=0.25)
```

The core idea while designing pya was to offer a set of data representations (Asig, Aspec, Astft) which provide straightforward access to the relevant data structures, and offer conversion methods, e.g. `Asig.to_spec()` or `Asig.to_stft()`, when operations in another reference frame are needed. These classes are accompanied by interface classes `Aserver` and `Arecorder` for playback and recording. `Aserver` features a timed queue to schedule data to be played at a given absolute or relative time. The package aims to minimize dependencies while maximizing flexibility. Particularly, the package features extensions to indexing and broadcasting as explained below.

3. CORE COMPONENTS OF PYA

In the current version (v0.3.1), pya features six classes and a set of helper functions. All classes except the signal generator class `Ugen` start with the letter 'A', which stands for *audio* just as the 'a' in pya (Python audio). The class diagram in Fig. 2 depicts the structure of the package. It contains the main signal class `Asig`, a spectrum class `Aspec` and a spectrogram class `Astft`. `Ugen` is a subclass of `Asig` that provides quick ways to generate commonly used signals. Then we have `Aserver` and `Arecorder` which in charge of audio playback and record.

3.1 Asig - The audio signal class

`Asig` is the core class of the library. An `Asig` object contains any audio array in the form of a `numpy.ndarray`, and other relevant information such as sampling rate, an identifier label, channel names, etc. The class offers a broad collection of methods commonly needed for audio signal processing. pya aims at making NumPy users automatically familiar with using pya for signal manipulation and is unique in providing 'numpythonic' indexing extensions.

There are multiple ways to create an `Asig` object, as shown in the code example below (see code comments for description):

```
1 from pya import Asig
2 from numpy.random import rand
3 asig0 = Asig(rand(44100, 2), sr=44100, label='
   noise', cn=['left', 'right']) # stereo noise
4 asig1 = Asig(sig="folder/filename.wav", label='
   filename') # Load an audio file
5 asig2 = Asig(1.2, sr=1000, channels=5) # A 1.2
   seconds, 5 channels zeros array at 1kHz
   sampling rate
6 asig3 = Asig(1024, sr=2048, channels=3) # A 3
   channels zeros array at 2048Hz sampling rate
   with 1024 sample frames
```

Listing 1. Several ways of constructing an `Asig` object

`Asig`'s constructor has 5 arguments: the required argument `sig` can be a NumPy array for audio signal, a string as path to a file, a float for creating a silence signal of given duration in seconds and an integer for an integer number of sample frames. The audio array is accessible at `Asig.sig`. `sr` as sampling rate is not required when loading an audio file but recommended for other cases, otherwise it defaults to 44100 Hz. Users can also specify the number of `channels`, yet the shape of a given `sig` takes priority. The `label` serves as a string identifier to the object. `cn`, short for 'channel names', is a list of strings for labelling each channel. This does not affect the signal array, but is useful for more meaningful sub-setting of channels, e.g., users might name a stereo signal's channel via `cn=['left', 'right']`, and index the wished channel as `asig[:, ['right']]`.

`Asig` offers a growing collection of methods for signal processing. Methods such as `gain()` enables gain

Figure 1. pya Class diagram.

adjustment in amplitude or decibel. `find_event()` enables detection of silence-separated events, `mono()` and `stereo()` convert audio signals to mono or stereo allowing to specify how to mix the original channels. The `plot()` method displays the `Asig` as time series, even allowing to stack line plots easily via `offset` and `scale` arguments, otherwise forwarding arguments as kwargs to the underlying Matplotlib `plot()`. `Asig` methods return either a new `Asig` object or `self`, which enables method chaining, resulting in a highly compact way to write signal processing paths.

`pya` extends the already powerful slicing of NumPy arrays to better tailor them for indexing segments of multi-channel audio – with particular benefits for code clarity and conciseness. As this topic is more complex, it will be expanded in the following subsection.

3.1.1 *Asig Indexing and Time Slicing*

One key feature of `Asig` is a set of methods to enable indexing, slicing and assignment, realized by defining `get_item` and `set_item` in similarity to NumPy, yet extending it for frequent audio use cases.

The pythonic way of sub-setting a list or a NumPy array is via index slicing. Slicing takes the form of `start:stop:step` and this is in analogy implemented for `Asigs`. However, when specifying audio segments, it is also common to use timestamps rather than the integer sample index. In `pya`, we introduced *time slicing* in addition to index slicing, allowing to pass timestamps in the form `{start:stop}`. Note that we chose the dictionary type here, as it allows to maintain the colon ‘:’ as familiar separator for slicing. An example is shown in Listing 2 with both the conventional index slicing and our newly introduced time slicing. Note that in analogy to index slicing, negative numbers refer to the position relative to the end, i.e. `a[-2:-1]` specifies the second last second of the signal `a`. Finally, note that different from standard slicing syntax, it is not possible to omit the `start` or `stop`. If the last two seconds

shall be selected, use `{-2:None}`. The reason is that dictionary syntax always requires key and value. Note that no `step` argument is allowed in time slicing.

```

1 __ = asig[0:150:2] # Index slicing with step 2
2 __ = asig[{0:1.5}] # Time slicing in seconds
  
```

Listing 2. `Asig` indexing

3.1.2 *Asig channel slicing, list slicing*

When dealing with multi-channel signals, sometimes we need to subset a subgroup of channels. Similar to the row slicing mentioned previously, column slicing utilizes the same pythonic principle. Specific to `pya`, we can give a list as column slicing argument. The data type of the list can be of type

- integer for column indices,
- boolean that chooses the columns that are true,
- string or list of strings for channel names from `cn`.

Listing 3 demonstrates the different options for the same indexing of channels. With the use of labeling each channel through `cn`, indexing audio channels can be done in a more linguistic way, which can offer more clarity to users.

```

1 asig = Asig(np.random.rand(5000, 5), cn=['fl', 'fr',
2         'cen', 'rl', 'rr']) # front-left to rear-right
3 asig[:, 0::2] # equiv. to [0,2,4]
4 asig[:, [True, False, True, False, True]]
5 asig[:, ['fl', 'cen', 'rr']]
  
```

Listing 3. 3 types of column indexing

3.1.3 *Broadcasting*

We implemented flexible ways of broadcasting signals to a subset of an `Asig` through `__setitem__()` such as `a1[{1.5:3}] = a2[{4:5.5}]`. Of course, this works

also for simultaneous channel subsetting. In such assignments, as signals are basically NumPy arrays, `Asig` follows the broadcasting rules of NumPy, i.e., a subset of the array can be reassigned by another. However, the conventional way requires equal shape. When working with audio data, mixing audio signals together, an equal shape is rarely given. This burdens users constantly with assuring in their code that assignments can be executed.

For example, in plain NumPy, mixing a signal `s2` into `s1` from index 300 would require `s1[300:300+s2.shape[1]] += s2`. An error will raise if `s1`'s length is not large enough to accommodate `s2`. It is likely users need to instantiate a new array to accommodate the potential new shaped signal resulting from that mix-shaped operation.

As a solution we invented and introduced into `pya` (as of now) three different *mix modes* for `__setitem__()`:

- **x** or **extend**. The extend mode automatically expands the destination's row dimension if the right-side operand (which can be either `Asig` or `ndarray`) has more rows than available.
- **b** or **bound**. The bound mode automatically fixates the shape of the left-side operand and thus truncates longer right-side operands.
- **o** or **overwrite**. This mode automatically replaces the left-side specified subset of the `Asig` with the right-side given signal, regardless of their lengths.

In search for the most compact, concise and readable way to enable these modes syntactically, we finally solved it by adding the `@properties` `x`, `b`, `o` to the `Asig` class. In their code, they merely set `self.mix_mode` to the specified mode value ('extend', 'bound', or 'overwrite') and then return `self`. In turn, the assignment `myasig.x[100:1000] = a2` makes sure that at the time the `__setitem__()` function of `myasig` is executed, the `mix_mode` flag has been properly set, allowing `setitem` to branch into mode-specific assignment code. Note that before exiting `setitem`, `mix_mode` is reset in order to avoid any confusion in subsequent/future assignments.

Both the abbreviation (`x`, `b`, `o`) and their corresponding full names can be used when setting the mix mode. Examples of `Asig` broadcasting are shown in Listing 4.

```

1 asig1[0:100, :] = asig2[100:200, :] # By default
  operands' shapes need to match
2
3 asig1.x[-10:] = np.arange(50) # assign 50 samples
  starting from last sample-10, i.e. asig1 is
  extended by 40 samples
4
5 asig1.bound[{-1.:}] += asig2[{-0:2.0}] # The first
  2 seconds of asig2 will be added to the end of
  asig1.
6
```

```

7 asig1.o[{-0.5:3.5}] = asig2[{-1.0:2.0}] # The
  resulting asig1 becomes shorter
```

Listing 4. Examples of `Asig` mixing modes. Note that here all `asigs` have the same sampling rate, thus equal duration corresponds to equal sample length.

3.2 Ugen - The unit generator class

`Ugen`, inherited from `Asig`, offers easy generation of several common waveforms, currently available are sine, cosine, square, sawtooth and noise. Each type of signal has its own method that returns an `Asig` object. All methods use optional arguments, by default they all return a 1s-signal at 44100 Hz with the amplitude of 1. For pitched signal, 440 Hz is the default frequency. An example is shown below:

```

1 from pya import Ugen
2 asine = Ugen().sine(freq=440, amp=1.0, dur=1.0,
  sr=44100, channels=1, cn='s', label='sine')
3 asquare = Ugen().square(freq=1000, amp=0.5,
  duty=0.3, dur=3.0, channels=3)
4 anoise = Ugen().noise(type='pink', amp=0.2, dur
  =0.5, sr=1000)
```

Listing 5. The unit generator class `Ugen` used to create sine, square and noise signals.

3.3 Aspec - The spectrum class

`Aspec` is the spectrum class, using `numpy.fft.rfft()` (Fig. 2). An `Aspec` object can be constructed directly by giving the required argument `x` as an `Asig` or a `numpy.ndarray`. Alternatively, the `to_spec()` method of `Asig` returns its `Aspec` counterpart. For multi-channel arrays, the spectrum of each channel is computed independently. Weighting functions can be applied to the spectrum of the signal. A warping function can be specified as argument of `.plot()`.

Figure 2. `Aspect` Spectrum plot, here a square wave via `Ugen().square(440, duty=0.5).to_spec().plot()`;

3.4 Astft - The STFT class

`Astft` generates the short-time-Fourier-transform using `scipy.signal.stft()`. Its `plot()` method displays the signal's spectrogram as a mesh plot (Fig. 3). Similar to `Aspec`, an `Astft` object can be created by converting an `Asig` object, e.g. `astft = asig.to_stft()`. Thus it can also be converted back to `Asig` object i.e. `asig = astft.to_sig()`.

Figure 3. Spectrogram of the sonification from Sec. 4.3.2, plotted via `son[:,1].to_stft().plot(ampdb)`

3.5 Aserver – The audio server class

`Aserver` allows users to boot a threaded audio stream playback server. At `Aserver`, users can set up the corresponding audio device and other parameters such as the sampling rate. Once the server is booted via `boot()`, audio data is streamed to the dedicated output. Users can not only trigger playback by calling the `Asig` object’s `play()` method, but also schedule a future playback, using the `onset` argument (relative in seconds or absolute using `time.time()`). Thus, multiple audio event playback can be orchestrated as needed simultaneously, overlapping or in sequence.

It is possible to construct multiple `Aserver` instances. In that way, it is possible to have multiple `Aserver` objects utilizing different audio devices at the same time. Below is an example of playing an `Asig` via different audio servers at different times.

```

1 from pya import Aserver, Ugen
2 as1 = Aserver(device=1).boot()
3 as2 = Aserver(device=4).boot()
4 saw = Ugen().sawtooth()
5 saw.play(server=as1, onset=1)
6 saw.play(server=as2, onset=2.5)

```

Listing 6. Playing an audio on multiple devices

The current version has not yet implemented sample-accurate synchronous playback to multiple devices. Thus simply calling two `play` methods does not result in a synchronized playback due to the processing required before the signal being queued to each server. We will work on this feature in the future release.

`pya` provides a helper function `device_info()` that prints all available devices and their information, from which users can find out the index of each device.

3.6 Arcorder – The audio recording class

Inherited from `Aserver`, `Arcorder` provides recording functionality. Booting a recorder object is similar to `Aserver`. Once booted, call `record()` to start and resume; `pause()` to pause and `stop()` to stop the recording. Afterwards, the current recording along with meta data will be stored as an `Asig` object and append to the `recordings` variables as a list of recordings.

At the time of publishing this paper, `Arcorder` has just been newly introduced to the package, thus various improvements will follow such as an easy way to

select one of multiple input channels, or to adjust the individual channel’s gain. We plan to introduce these the upcoming release of `pya`.

3.7 helpers – A collection of useful functions

In addition to the main class components, `pya` contains a collection of helper functions that can be imported and used, such as the aforementioned `device_info()`. Others include conversions, e.g., between amplitude and decibel (`ampdb` and `dbamp`), or a linear-to-linear mapping (`linlin`). Furthermore there are functions for normalization (`normalize`), clipping (`clip`), conversion between cycle-per-second (`cps`) and MIDI (`midicps` and `cpsmidi`), etc. Many helper functions are named and defined in analogy to `SuperCollider3` functions.

4. EXAMPLES

In this section, we present three examples to demonstrate some of the possible usages of `pya`.

4.1 Sound Synthesis with pya

In the first example let’s create a band-limited square wave using additive synthesis, i.e., by summing few terms of the Fourier series

$$x(t) = \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2k-1} \sin(2\pi(2k-1)f \cdot t) \quad (1)$$

As shown in Fig. 4, we zip the vectors of frequencies and amplitudes (odd harmonics and reciprocal amplitudes), summing the sine waves generated by `Ugen()` by looping through the total amount of units.

```

1 asig = Asig(1.0) # Create a blank canvas
2 harmonics = (1 + 2 * np.arange(100))
3 for f, a in zip(3*harmonics, 1/harmonics):
4     asig += Ugen().sine(f, a, sr=44100, dur=1.)

```


Figure 4. Additive synthesis of 100 sine waves to form a 1 s, 3 Hz band-limited square wave signal.

4.2 Multi-channel audio processing

Due to the flexibility of indexing and broadcasting mentioned in Section 3, `pya` is highly suited for multi-channel audio editing or playback. Fig. 5 demonstrates arranging a 4 channels mix. First, an `Asig` with the correct number of channels but only 1 sample is constructed as a placeholder. Using the `extend`

```

a = Asig(1, sr=1000, channels=4, cn=['a', 'b', 'c', 'd'], label='multichannel')
b = Ugen().sine(freq=50, sr=1000, dur=0.6).fade_in(0.3).fade_out(0.2)
a.x[:, 'a'] = 0.2 * b # no need to extend as len(src)<len(dest)
a.x[300:, 'b'] = 0.5 * b # extends a to 0.9 seconds
a.x[1300:, 'c'] = 0.2 * b[1:2] # extends a further, writing beyond end
a.x[1900:, 'd'] = 0.2 * b[300:] # note that 3 is 'd'
plt.figure(figsize=(12,3)); a.plot(offset=1, scale=3.5)

```

Asig('multichannel'): 4 x 2200 @ 1000Hz = 2.200s cn=['a', 'b', 'c', 'd']

Figure 5. Sequencing signals in a 4-channel audio.

mode `x`, we mix signals in while extending `Asig` as needed beyond the end. Note that zero-padding is automatically applied to other channels on extension.

For stereo, the same principle as above can be applied. `Asig` features methods such as `stereo()` for arbitrary blending and `pan2()` for constant power panning to a stereo position in $[-1, 1]$ (left, right).

4.3 Sonification

Sonification is the systematic, reproducible representation of data using sound [12]. There are a variety of sonification techniques to represent complex data, such as audification, parameter-mapping sonification, model-based sonification etc, see the Sonification Handbook [13] for an overview. As data is often processed and analyzed with `ipython`, it is convenient to have basic sonification methods available without the requirement to interface with other sound synthesis engines such as `Supercollider` or `PureData`. Also, there sometimes is the situation that complex (beyond realtime renderability) mappings force offline sonification anyway, and `pya` lends itself both for simple and fast sonification tasks and complex offline mappings. For the demo we merely feature the example notebooks made available as supplementary material to the paper, available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.4119/unibi/2938412>. Due to limited space, we here focus on audification and parameter-mapping sonification.

4.3.1 Audification

Audification is basically the direct data-as-sound translation for auditory inspection of time series [13]. We demonstrate how `pya` can help with an example of auditory analysis of EEG data. The example notebook (see supplementary material) loads a provided data set by

```

1 data = np.loadtxt("data/epileptic-eeeg.csv",
2   delimiter=",")
3 chnls = "FP1 FP2 F3 F4 C3 C4 P3 P4 O1 O2 F7
4   F8 T7 T8 P7 P8 FZ CZ PZ".split(" ")
5 aeeeg = Asig(data, sr=256.41, cn=chnls)

```

This shows by the way that `Asigs` are also useful to represent and manipulate non-audio data such as biomedical data. We can now audify and plot for instance channel 5 and 9 at a 10x-speedup

in one line of code: `a1=aeeeg[:,5, 9].norm(1).plot().resample(44100, rate=10).play()` In the provided sound example, we hear the rhythmical (3/sec) epileptic pattern arising and falling back into background signal. Listening at higher speedup (25×) via `a1 = aeeeg[:,5, 9].norm(1).resample(44100, rate=25).play()`, we discover the *ritardando* over the seizure. Next, let's select 6 seconds (from 16s–22s), to listen in 'slow motion'. We resample to a modest 8000 Hz audio rate by `a2 = aeeeg[16:22].norm(1).plot(scale=0.5, offset=1).resample(8000, rate=1)`.

However, we better modulate the signal – here with a sine wave – since otherwise we would not perceive the low frequencies. So, let's (i) use integer multiples of 90 Hz for the series of channels, (ii) listen to the result in $1/2\times$ the original speed, (iii), plot the compiled audio with a thin green line, and (iv), save the audio file in WAV format. This complex task can be performed with 4 lines of code:

```

1 asum = Asig(a2.get_duration(), sr=a2.sr)
2 for i in range(a2.channels):
3     asum += a2[:, i] * Ugen().sine(90*(i+1), dur=
4       a2.get_duration(), sr=a2.sr)
5 asum.norm().plot(color="g", lw=0.1).stereo().play
6   (rate=0.5).save_wavfile('eeg.wav')

```

This showcases that a quite complex set of tasks can be easily expressed in short and concise code, which is even shorter than the textual instruction above, yet remains well readable.

4.3.2 Parameter Mapping Sonification

Next we demonstrate `pya` for discrete parameter-mapping sonification, i.e., data variables are mapped to synthesis parameters and the resulting sound events are mixed to the sound track. Our parameters will be onset, frequency, duration, amplitude and stereo panning. For the demo, we use the well-known Iris data set of 4 geometric features of 150 iris plants¹. With `pya`, a 5-parameter synthesizer can be written highly compact as Python function:

```

1 def mysyn(freq=440, dur=0.34, amp=0.9, att
2   =0.01, pan=0.5):
3     return Ugen().sine(freq, dur=float(dur), sr
4       =8000).fade_in(0.01).envelope([0,1,0], [0, att,
5       dur], curve=4).gain(amp).stereo([1-pan, pan])

```

With it, the parameter-mapping becomes

```

1 son = Asig(1.0, sr=8000, channels=2)
2 for i, v in enumerate(iris):
3     onset = mapcol(v, 2, 0, 4) # def: s. .ipynb
4     freq = mapcol(v, 1, 200, 2000)
5     # some lines skipped here for code brevity
6     son.x[onset:None] += mysyn(freq, dur, amp,
7       0.001, pan)
8 son.norm().plot(offset=1, alpha=0.5).play()

```

Note how the extend mix-mode facilitates superimposing data-driven sound events into the sound canvas `son`.

¹ see <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/iris>

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We have introduced `pya`, a new audio processing package with the aim to make audio coding more pythonic by exploring and extending NumPy and SciPy coding styles, incorporating and thus hiding many tedious coding work into a set of audio classes `Asig` for signals, `Aspec` for spectra, `Astft` for spectrograms and `Aserver/Arecorder` as interfaces for real-time and non-blocking playback/recording.

Conceptually new contributions are *time slicing* and broadcasting via *mix_modes*. They alone simplify many audio coding problems, according to our own experience. Being still a novel and young package, some `pya` interfaces may be changed on deeper understanding or better ideas how to write code even more elegantly. However, the core functionality should only mature or improve.

The examples in this paper demonstrate that `pya` can be swiftly used for very different tasks, resulting in short, clean and readable code, and we hope that future contributions and extensions help to make it more versatile and useful.

The roadmap for future releases will involve improvements on the freshly added `Arecorder` class for non-blocking audio recording, additional audio backends such as Web Audio, full documentation and tutorials, custom meta data, introducing more audio processing algorithms and effects, instrument class for designing digital musical instruments with MIDI support, etc.

`pya` is hosted under our github organization *Interactive-Sonification* and available on PyPI and Github. It is under MIT license and we are eager to hear comments, feature requests, and to discuss ideas.

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